

Review Article

Consumers' Impulse Buying Behavior: Structured Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

To be successful in business the marketers must have understanding of how consumers behave on every occasion during an implicit or explicit need for a product. The knowledge of consumer behavior involves both the physical, mental and emotional process is helpful and worthwhile for the marketing institutions to recognize how the buyer thinks, feels, and selects products from a given alternatives and how those consumers are influenced by different factors. The consumers can purchase products either through planning or impulsively on the spot decisions. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the factors that determine consumers impulse buying behavior. To achieve the stated objectives the study has employed structured systematic literature review by identifying and obtaining the per-reviewed article published since 2011 from google scholar, ResearchGate, science direct, winey online, Taylor & Francis and emerald database. From totally extracted 176 articles, 29 articles were satisfied the inclusion criteria and further reviewed for this article analysis purpose. The outcome of this study has shown that store environment related factors, demographic factors, personality traits and situational factors are influencing consumer impulse buying behavior.

Keywords: Consumer behavior, impulse buying, impulse buying behavior

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Introduction

Marketing of any products mainly depends on understanding of how consumers behave on every occasion during an implicit or explicit need for a product. A consumer is an individual who purchases or ability to purchase products that offered for sale by marketers to satisfy personal or household needs, wants or desires. The knowledge of consumer behavior consists of both the mental and emotional process is helpful and worthwhile for the marketing institutions to recognize how the buyer thinks, feels, and selects products from a given alternatives and how those consumers are influenced by different factors. Therefore, as a marketer gains profit from trading with customer, understanding of the consumer behavior is significant tool for the success of business in an ever-changing business environment (Sadikoglu & Sadikoglu, 2017). In the marketing context, the term “consumer behavior” refers to both pre-purchase and post-purchase activities (Sadikoglu & Sadikoglu, 2017). Pre-purchase activities are related with searching for products that might satisfy a consumer while post-purchase activities are concerned with satisfaction related to the purchased item in use. As such studying a consumer issue is an important dimension for both marketers and researcher to understand consumers behavior and thought.

Consumer behavior is the process of collecting and organizing information for a purchase decision and of using and evaluating goods and services. It contains certain decisions, activities, ideas or experiences that satisfy consumer needs and wants (Solomon, 1996). Consumer behavior involves the study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy, why they buy, where they buy, how often they buy, how often they use, how they evaluate after the purchase and the impact of such evaluations on future purchases, and how they dispose of it (Ahuja, 2015; Singh et al., 2014). It is concerned with all activities directly involved in obtaining, using and disposing of products, including the decision processes that antecedents and follow the actions (Blackwell, Miniard, & Engel, 2001). This process includes the stages of searching for products, evaluation, purchasing, using and disposing of products.

As consumers are exposed to many stimulants, their purchases decisions are influenced by many factors which enables them to make certain decision. Therefore, those investments by marketers made in product design, packaging, quality distinction, advertising, sales promotion must aimed at persuading the customer to make favorable decisions towards a firm’s product (Goodhope et al., 2013). Consequently, the marketing institution must aware that the consumer can purchase products thoroughly planned, partially planned, and unplanned manner (Blackwell, Miniard, and Engel 2012; Troilo 2015). This is to mean that consumer may purchase product through careful planning and evaluating before purchase decision or the consumers can purchase specific products without planning on the spot. Therefore, buying decision in impulse buying is unplanned before purchase, probably accompanied by little information search and alternatives evaluation and short decision- time due to the characteristics of products and services (Kang, 2013; Karim et al., 2020). It is characterized by unplanned, on-the spot decision, resulted from reaction to a stimulus and involve either emotional or cognitive reaction, or both (Harmancioglu et al., 2009). Impulse buying is a universal aspect of consumer behavior and one of the main considerations for marketing activities due to the complexity

and wide-spread incidence of impulse buying across various types of products (Sharma et al., 2010 as cited in Chang et al., 2014).s

The study by Mattila and Wirtz (2012) shown that unplanned impulse purchases account for up to 60% of all purchases, and that impulse purchase can account from 40%to80% of purchases depending on product type (Hausman, 2010; Kacen, Hess, & Walker, 2012). Additionally, (Point-of- Purchase Advertising International [PPAI],2012) study reported that 76% of all purchase decisions are made in the store were impulse purchase, and similar study conducted by National Endowment for Financial Education (NEFI,2015) claimed that more than 87% of American adults disclose on making impulse purchases. On the same token, the study by Coca Cola revealed that impulse buying accounts for over 50% of all grocery purchases (CNBC, 2009 as cited in Amos et al., 2013). In addition, the study by Tuttle (2012) shown that 52% of the Millennial generation are more likely to make an impulse purchase than any other generation. Moreover, more than half of purchases are spontaneous(Maymand & Ahmadinejad, 2011). Consequently, other studies in the field shown that 27-80% of general purchase are unplanned and occur due to sudden decisions(Khan et al., 2015). Additionally, based on the prior studies conducted in different countries on impulsive buying , the occurrence of impulsive buying was 7 percent in Germany in 2007 (Mueller, et al., 2011), 13 percent in Spain (Otero-López & Villardefrancos, 2014), 16.4 percent in United kingdom in 2017 (Maccarrone-Eaglen & Schofield, 2017) and 29.1 percent with in China (He, Kukar-Kinney, & Ridgway, 2018) . This indicates that impulse buying is common across countries and critical to a retailers' profit. For this reason, marketers and researcher tend to increase understanding and knowledge on influential factors and the effects of those factors on impulse buying behavior. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the factors that determine the consumers impulse buying behavior.

Theoretical foundation

This section is structured as follows. The first section presents the concepts, factors influencing consumer behavior and consumer buying process. Followed by concepts of consumers impulse buying, types of impulse buying, process of consumers impulse buying and factors influencing consumer impulse buying behavior.

Consumer Behavior

Concept of Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, evaluate, purchase, use or dispose of products, ideas or experiences that satisfy needs and wants (Solomon, Bamossy, Askegaard, & Hogg, 2006). Taking similar approach, Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) express consumer behavior as the behavior that consumers show in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services that they think will satisfy their needs. According to Priest, Carter, and Statt (2013) CB is the mental, emotional and physical activities of consumers discloses during searching, selecting, purchasing, using and disposing of products and services in order to satisfy needs and desires. It is the study of the behavior of purchasing and disposing of services, goods, experiences or ideas by the individuals, groups and

organizations so as to satisfy their needs and wants (Kotler & Keller, 2011). Kotler and Armstrong (2010) stated consumer behavior as the buying behavior of final consumers that buy goods and services for personal consumption.

Factors influencing consumer's buying behavior

Consumers are exposed to many stimulants which influence them to take certain action for buying specific products. There are four major factors that influence consumer's buying behavior which consists of cultural, social, personal, and psychological characteristics (Joshi & Rahman, 2016; Kotler & Armstrong, 2010; Kotler & Keller, 2015; Ramya & Ali, 2016)

Cultural factors: - These factors are often innate in our values and decision process that includes a consumer's culture, subculture and social class.

Social factors: - refer to forces that other people exert on consumers' purchase decisions either affect directly or indirectly. These factors contain groups i.e., reference groups, aspirational groups and member groups, family, roles and status.

Personal factors: Which include those characteristics that are unique to a person and influence purchase behavior. These factors include demographic factors i.e., age, sexes, lifecycle stage, occupation, economic circumstances, lifestyle, personality and situational factors.

Psychological factors: - are internal to individual and generates forces within individual that affecting purchase decision. This factor consists of motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes.

Consumer buying decision process

According to Armstrong (1991) the purchase decision process is the phases a consumer passes through in making choices about which products to buy. It is a process used by consumer in the market before, during and after the purchase products. It starts with need recognition and end with the post purchase behavior of consumers. The conventional view of consumers purchasing decision-making process involves five steps (Dixit et al., 2019).

Need Recognition: - The decision of buying begins with the recognizing the need or desire for a specific product that satisfy wants. The strength of need decides the priority list of the consumer were consumer make an immediate purchase of those products which are most important for them and postpone the other need or desire.

Information Search: - The need identified at first stage can be satisfied when the consumer distinguishes what product can satisfy that need and availability of that product. Once the consumer identified his/her needs, the consumer looks for the information from various sources such as family, friends, advertisement, media etc.

Evaluation of Alternative: - The consumer search for and evaluates various alternatives products that satisfy their needs. In evaluating process, the consumer looks at various aspects of products and services in the form of features, utility, brand image and

post purchase services. The criteria that the consumer used to evaluate the product vary and mainly depending on the situation and the involvement of the consumer.

Purchase Decision: - After evaluating all the alternatives in the market purchase of specific products depends on the evaluation criteria, ranking and affordability by consumer. At this stage the sellers should support the buyer by providing sufficient information about products in decision making process to reduce risk.

Post-Purchase Behavior: - At this stage the consumer evaluates the performance of the product, and either satisfied or dissatisfied with the product performance. If the product performance matches the consumer expectation, consumers will repeat the purchase and result in positive publicity. On the other hand, if performance falls short of expectation the consumer will halt buying and the buyer will talk negatively about the product.

Impulse Buying

Concepts of impulsive Buying

Impulsive buying is unplanned purchase without careful consideration and rational decision-making process owing to a powerful stimulus (Iyer et al., 2019 as cited in Ahn & Kwon, 2020). Similarly Rook and Gardner (1993) defined impulse buying as unplanned behavior involving sudden decision-making and tendency for urgent acquisition of the product. It is urgent buying without any prior-shopping objective which is often accompanied by feelings of excitement, pleasure and/or a powerful and persistent urge to buy (Beatty & Ferrell, 1998). It is sudden, compelling, hedonically complex buying behavior in which the rapidity of an impulse decision process prevents thoughtful and deliberate consideration of alternative information and choices (Bayley & Nancarrow, 1998). According to Morwitz (2007) impulse buying is the buying of products with least deliberation under the influence of a sudden and powerful urge. Therefore, impulse buying is coming from impulsive behavior which is irresistibly arousing but less deliberative as compared to planned purchasing conducts.

Types of Impulse Buying

Han et al. (1991) classified Impulse Buying Behavior into four types: Planned impulse buying: - spontaneous purchases made by consumers without any certainty of buying what products but have planned to shop when leaving for the shop (Made & Ketut, 2018). Reminded impulse buying:- impulsive purchases made by consumers when consumer remembers that he/she needs it and decides to purchase the product in the shop, Suggestion impulse buying: Purchases are made when the consumer sees the product, sees the usage procedure or benefits and decides to make a purchase (Japariato and Sugiharto 2011) and Pure impulse buying:- buying is done by consumers as the result of emotional connections so that they purchase products outside of their buying habits so that this is purely resulted from the internal conditions of consumers.

According to Ko (1993) unplanned buying maybe divided into three types: Reasonable unplanned buying related to both objective evaluation and emotional preferences,

emotional impulse buying related with only emotional preferences and objective impulse buying associated with only objective evaluation.

Process of Impulse buying

Churchill and Peter (1998) developed impulse buying model which has been later modified by Kim (2003) to describe the impulse buying process by overlooking several steps i.e. need recognition, information search, and alternative evaluation, and reclassifying influencing factors. The impulse buying process begins with product awareness/ browsing without having an intention to purchase a certain item or visiting a certain store. As consumers search or browse, they are exposed to the many stimuli and feel the desire to buy. Then the impulse buyer makes a purchase decision without searching for information or evaluating alternatives. After the purchase, the post-purchase evaluation may experience positive or negative consequences. In this process, consumers are influenced by external factors (window display, visual merchandising, in-store form display, floor merchandising, promotional signage) and internal (mood, need/desire, hedonic pleasure, cognitive or affective evaluation) that trigger their impulse purchase behavior.

Figure 1 A model of Impulse buying process
 Source: Kim (2003) as cited in (Tinne, 2010)

Factors Influencing Impulse Buying Behavior

There are several factors that plays a significant role to take customers to the final decision in buying a particular product. Therefore, it is very crucial for the marketing team to understand the factors that influence the consumers purchasing process and impulse buying decision.

Store environment

Chang et al., (2011) adopted survey study to understand whether and how characteristics of the retail environment influence impulse buying behavior through the mediating role of consumers' positive emotional responses in USA. The data was collected using questionnaires by a store intercept method from 212 consumers of a locally owned retail stores and analyzed through descriptive and regression analysis. The

study found that the retail environment i.e., ambient/ design characteristics has direct effects on consumers' positive emotional responses to the retail environment which in turn, consumers' positive emotional responses to the retail environment affects impulse buying behavior. Similarly Chang et al., (2014) investigated direct and indirect effects of apparel store environmental characteristics and consumers' positive emotional responses to the environment on impulse buying behavior. Primary data was collected from 118 female consumers of an outdoor retail store in the western region of the USA using a store intercept method. Regression analysis were applied to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study revealed that direct effects of the store ambient/design characteristics (i.e., ambient, design, and social) on positive emotional responses to the retail environment and direct effects of positive emotional responses (more excited, enthusiastic, fun, happy, interested, inspired, and joyful) on impulse buying behavior. Moreover, two situational characteristics i.e., money availability, task definition moderated the relationships between retail environmental characteristics and consumers' emotional responses to the environment while time availability did not moderate the relationship between consumers' impulse buying behavior and positive emotional response.

Akram et al., (2016) employed cross sectional study to explore the relationship between store atmosphere and impulse buying behavior (IBB) through moderating role of demographic variable in stores of Pakistan. Data was collected from seven hundred individuals through self-administered questionnaire from the eighteen retail stores in three big cities (Faisalabad, Lahore and Islamabad) of Pakistan. Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis and structured equation modeling was used for the analysis of data and the hypotheses was tested with the aid of SPSS and AMOS 20. The results of the study shown that store atmosphere has positive relationship and significant influence on impulse buying behavior. Additionally, it reveals that only one demographic variable i.e., age has substantial influence on impulse buying behavior while gender and education bear insignificant relationship with IBB. Therefore, apart from gender and education, age moderates the relationship between store atmosphere and impulse buying behavior. In India, Parsad et al., (2017) assessed the role of store environment, impulsive buying personality traits, impulsive buying tendency, and urge to buy on impulsive buying. Data was gathered from 203 respondents and analyzed with the aid of AMOS 22.0 software. The finding of the study showed that impulse buying was positively associated with impulse buying tendency and urge to buy. The most important finding of the study is the significant effect of store environment (crowd, sales employee, entertainment, lighting, aroma and display) on consumers impulse buying. The study also indicated that consumers impulsive traits do not directly lead to impulse buying.

The study conducted in restaurant by Lu and Su (2018) in order to analyze the influence of dining environment and reference group on customers' impulse buying behavior. Data was collected through questionnaires from 484 customers of Japanese and American restaurants in Taipei City, Taiwan by applying random sampling techniques. Descriptive statistics, reliability, exploratory factor, correlation and regression analysis were employed to analysis data with the help of SPSS 18. The findings showed that social factors, influence of reference group and extraversion were three factors that affect customers' impulse buying behavior. Consequently, Durai and Stella (2020) studied to find out factors that influence the impulse buying behaviors in store atmospherics of apparel stores with reference to Chennai city, India. The study employed convenience

sampling method to collect primary data through structured questionnaires from 110 consumers across various retail outlets. The exploratory factor analysis was used to determine the essential elements of impulse buying using SPSS version 20. The outcomes of the study revealed that store exterior atmospherics takes the most effects on consumer impulse purchasing followed by visual merchandising, store interior atmospherics, store layout and store display. At the same year Arthur et al., (2020) conducted survey study to examine the determinants of consumer impulsive purchasing behavior of Ghanaian shoppers. The study used to examine the selected five external factors like in-store browsing, in-store atmosphere, in-store layout, sales- person, promotional activities, store environment and reference groups variables to determine the consumer impulsive purchasing behavior. Convenience sampling technique was used to collect primary data through online survey from 180 respondents from three shopping places in Accra and Kumasi, Ghana. Multiple regression and correlational analysis were used to determine the impact and relationship between consumer's impulsive purchasing behavior and five variables using AMOS in Statistical Packages for Social Sciences' (SPSS) software. The outcome of the study exhibited that sales personnel, store atmosphere and promotional activities are best determinants of impulsive purchasing behavior while in-browsing and reference groups insignificant to determine impulsive purchasing behavior.

Demographic characteristics

Chavosh et al., (2011) conducted study in Singapore to evaluate the impact of product characteristics and consumer characteristics on Singaporean consumer's impulse purchasing behavior. The primary data was collected through questionnaire from 100 customers using simple random sampling technique from three major shopping centers in Singapore. Chi-square analysis was used to examine the variable relationships with the aid of SPSS. The finding of the study indicated that gender (more popular among women rather than men), age (young consumers do more impulse buying rather than older consumers), mood (people with a negative mood are more likely to do impulse buying), shopping enjoyment and impulse buying tendency have impact on the consumer's impulse buying behavior whereas the variable of materialism doesn't have any significant impact on the consumer's impulse buying behavior among Singaporean consumers. This study also exhibited a significant relationship between product characteristics and consumers' impulse purchasing behavior in Singapore. At the same year, Ghani and Jan (2011) investigated the relationship between demographic factors and impulse buying tendency of consumers in the urban areas of Pakistan, a developing country. The primary data was collected from 100 customers from retail store with the help of questionnaires and analyzed using multiple regressions analysis method with the aid of SPSS. The outcome of the study indicated that age has a significant negative relationship with the impulse buying tendency while income and gender are insignificantly related with impulse buying behavior.

On the other hand, Ekeng et al., (2012) employed descriptive cross-sectional study design to examine the effect of consumers' demographic characteristics on impulse buying. Data was gathered using purposive sampling technique through structured questionnaire from 400 consumers in marketplaces, supermarkets and high traffic point areas across Calabar Metro. Data were analyzed using tables, simple percentages, Pearson's correlation, independent samples test and multiple regression analysis by

means of SPSS 17 software. The outcome of study revealed that consumer's demographic characteristic has significant influence impulse buying. More specifically, the finding of the study showed that age of consumers and impulse buying were significantly, and inversely related while impulse buying differs significantly between male and female consumers with the impulse buying phenomenon is more common among female shoppers. In addition, education in this study is observed to exert tremendous influence on impulse buying, because higher positions in the society are determined by consumers' educational qualification which in turn affects their salary scale, thereby boosting their ego to purchase products which could be planned or unplanned for because of the purchasing power of money. On the other hand, Ali and Hasnu (2013) investigated the relationship between impulse buying and consumers characteristics i.e. gender, age, income, geographical orientation and cultural orientation. Primary data was collected through close-ended questionnaires from randomly selected 100 buyers from various shopping centers of Abbottabad and Islamabad, Pakistan. The study applied descriptive analysis, independent Sample t-Test, One-Way ANOVA, and correlation to analyze data. The outcome of the study shown that there is no significant variable that can influence consumers to buy on impulse. Similarly, Cheng et al., (2013) examined the effect of shopping companion gender on impulse purchase behavior. The finding of their study indicated that shoppers were more likely to show impulse purchase behavior when shopping with an opposite gender companion.

Ugbomhe et al. (2018) adopted descriptive cross-sectional research design to determine the effects of demographic factors age, gender, income, education, marital status and occupation on impulse buying behavior of consumers in Auchi, Nigeria. The study implemented convenience sampling techniques to collect data from 384 respondents with the help of structured questionnaires and used multiple regression analysis with the aid of SPSS 20 to analyze data. The results of the study revealed that demographic characteristics i.e., age, gender, income, education, marital status had significant relationship with impulse buying behavior of consumers. On the other hand, Farid and Ali (2018) adopted explanatory research design to study the impact of personality traits i.e. openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism on impulse buying behavior. Data was obtained from 400 respondents using structured questionnaires with the help of non-probability sampling using mall intercept technique. Factor analysis and multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the collected data. The result of the study indicated significant positive effects of openness, extraversion, conscientiousness, and neuroticism while agreeableness had negative and insignificant effect on impulse buying behavior.

Creev and Furnham (2019) studied the relationship between demographic, personality and attitudinal factors and impulsive buying. Data was derived through secondary analysis from common participants in two large national surveys of British adults: one survey contributing data on impulsive buying, money attitudes and demographics; and the second, a Big Five personality trait measure. The finding of the study shown that demographic variable being youth, female, and higher household income were positively associated with impulsive buying. In personality traits low openness and conscientiousness but high extraversion and neuroticism were positively associated with impulsive buying. Finally, associating money with freedom, power or love increased likelihood of impulse buying and associating money with security decreased likelihood

of impulsive buying. The study by Ahmad et al., (2019) explored the relationship between individual differences and impulse buying behavior directly and indirectly through the mediating role of positive mood. The study adopted survey methods and collected data from 300 customers in Lahore using convenience sampling techniques and analyzed using PLS based structural equation model. The outcome of the study indicated that positive mood, impulse buying tendency and fashion involvement are factors significantly affect impulse buying behavior while self-esteem, shopping enjoyment and hedonism are insignificant variables for impulse buying. Self-esteem, impulse buying tendency, hedonism and self-esteem have a direct significant impact with the role of mediating variable positive mood whereas fashion involvement shows insignificant relation with Purchasing mood. The Findings of the study also exhibited that fashion involvement, positive mood and impulse buying play an important role as motivator of individuals for spontaneous buying.

Barakat (2019) investigated factors affecting consumers' impulsive buying tendency in shopping malls. The Study examined the relationship between consumers' personal traits, consumers' demographic characteristics, situational variables related to consumer and store, and consumers' impulsive buying tendency. In this study, questionnaires were used as a tool for collecting primary data from 1380 consumer respondents and analyzed using SPSS 16.0 and Amos.18. The results of the study indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship between consumers' personal traits i.e., shyness, emotional stability, materialism, collectivism and impulsive buying tendency while the relationship between individualism and impulsive buying tendency is significant and negative. Additionally, the study revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between situational variables like credit card use, time availability, shopping enjoyment and impulsive buying tendency. Moreover, the study has shown that there is a significant and positive relationship between store's sales promotions, store's sales associates, and impulsive buying tendency. More specifically, the finding of the study showed that women consumers have greater tendency to impulsive buying than men consumers, young consumers have greater tendency to impulsive buying than old consumers and high-income consumers have more tendency to impulsive buying than low-income consumers. Also the study by Ali and Zubairi (2020) adopted quantitative research method to determine the influence of demographic factors i.e., age, gender, and income on the impulse buying behavior (IBB) of the consumers of supermarkets. The questionnaire was designed as a tool for collecting primary data from 300 respondents using convenience sampling technique. The study executed descriptive analysis, reliability analysis, and regression analysis using SPSS for testing the stated hypothesis of the study. The finding of the study indicated that the demographic factors significantly influence pure impulse buying behavior. Likewise the other study concluded that female gender identity positively affected impulse buying behavior, whereas masculine gender identity did not affect impulse buying behavior (Ozdemir & Akcay, 2019)

Personality characteristics

The study by Jyoti and Verma (2014) examined the effect of five intrinsic factors i.e. personality, culture, materialism, shopping enjoyment tendency, and impulsive buying tendency on impulsive buying behavior. The questionnaire was used to collect data from 508 respondents by using convenience sampling technique. Data was analyzed with

confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling using AMOS version 20.0. The outcome the study showed that materialism, shopping enjoyment tendency, and impulsive buying tendency had significant positive relationship with impulsive buying behavior. The study also showed that cultural construct of collectivism and two personality constructs of extraversion and conscientiousness has significant relationship with impulsive buying behavior. Similarly, Mathai and Haridas (2014) applied descriptive research design to investigate the influence of /relations between the impulse buying on/and different personality traits among the retail customers in Kochin city. The structured closed ended questionnaire was used to collect data from 70 respondents of various retail outlet customers through simple random method. Descriptive statistics were used to describe and summarize data while ANOVA to identify the relationship between personality and impulse buying behavior via SPSS 20.0. The study revealed the existence of a relationship between personality traits and impulse buying behavior. More specifically, the study shown that extrovert personalities are making more impulse purchases than others. Likewise, Veeerayekanna and Latha (2016) studied the role of the external factors on influencing impulse buying behavior with respect to personality of individual. To achieve the stated objective one way ANOVA was carried out to verify the difference observed among the different personality traits. The test carried out indicated that extrovert personalities are making more impulse purchases than others. Other study conducted in India by Atulkar and Kesari (2017) to figure out the relationship between consumer trait and impulse buying. The structured questionnaires were used to collect primary data from 375 consumers from different organized retail stores in central India through convenience sampling method. Structural equation model was used to analyze collected data using SmartPLS 2.0 statistical software. The finding of the study indicated that impulse interpersonal influence, buying tendency, emotional attachment and materialism show significant positive relationship with impulsive buying, whereas the shopping enjoyment tendency showed significant relationship and negative effects.

Chein et al., (2020) conducted survey study to identify the influence of two internal (conscientiousness and extraversion traits) and four external factors (individualism, impulse buying tendency trait, visual merchandising factors and price) on impulsive buying in Malaysia. Primary data was collected from a total of 200 respondents via mall-intercept method from different shopping malls in Melaka, Malaysia using convenience sampling methods. Structural equation technique (SEM) was used to analysis and validate the proposed hypothesis with the aid of Smart-PLS 3.0 software program. The outcome of the study shown that except for conscientiousness which has negative influence on impulse buying behavior, the predictors of extraversion traits, individualism, impulse buying tendency trait, visual merchandising, and price have positive influence on impulse buying behavior. More specifically, the study revealed that there is a negative or inverse relationship between conscientiousness and impulsive buying behavior while extraversion trait relates positively with impulsive buying behavior. On the other hand, individualism influences impulsive buying behavior in a positive manner. The finding of this study also exhibited the significant and positive relationship between impulse buying tendency trait and impulsive buying behavior. Moreover, the visual merchandising component (window display, in-store form/ mannequin display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage) is found to be statistically and significantly related to impulsive buying behavior.

Situational factor

Karbasivar and Yarahmadi (2011) examined the effect of four external cues (window display, credit card, promotional activities (cash discount, free product) on consumer impulse buying behavior in Abadan, Iran. The study adopted purposive sampling techniques to gather primary data through questionnaires from 275 sample respondents. Descriptive statistics and structural equation modelling were used to analysis data with the help of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences' (SPSS) and LISREL software. The result of study exhibited the existence of positive relationship between window display, credit card, promotional activities (discount, free product) and consumer impulse buying behavior. Foroughi et al., (2012) determined the influence of the time and money availability on impulse purchase among different ethnics. Convenience sampling method was used to collect data through questionnaires from 130 respondents in Malaysia (Chinese, Indians, Malay people) and used Path analysis to measure the effect of variables. The outcome of the study revealed that the situational variables (money available and Time available) were influence impulse buying. The quantitative study was employed by Ahmed and Parmar (2014) to explore the factors that affect impulsive buying behavior for FMCGs goods in Larkana and surrounding territories, Pakistan. The study used both primary and secondary data to find out the results. The study employed convince sampling method to collect primary data through questionnaires from 384 sample respondents. The descriptive and correlation analysis was used to analysis data with the aid of SPSS software. The outcome of the study shown that income level and visual merchandising (well decorated, with pleasant and calm store environment along with colorful surroundings) has highly and significantly influence on consumer's impulse buying for fast moving consumer goods/products in Larkana, Pakistan. Therefore, well-designed window displays with insertion up a proper placement of products, packaging and displays of products along with a better presentation of products and store can stimulate consumers for impulse purchase. Likewise, Jyoti and Verma (2015) undertaken the study to assess the role of situational variables in impacting impulsive buying behavior. The authors propose nine situational variables—categorized as personal (money availability, economic wellbeing, family influence, time availability, and credit card use), and in-store (sales promotion, store environment, friendly store employees, and store music) to understand such factors influence on buying behavior. The study utilized purposive sampling technique to collect data from 508 mall visiting customers and analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling. The finding of the study shown that all five personal factors were found to be impacting impulsive buying behavior. On the other side, among in-store variables sales promotion, friendly store employees, and store environment were found to significantly impact the impulsive buying behavior while store music was found to be unrelated to impulsive buying behavior. At the same year, Khorrami et al., (2015) adopted quantitative research with descriptive approach to identify the effect of situational factors on impulse buying and compulsive buying. The study adopted random sampling techniques to collect data which was analyzed using LISREL Software. The results of the study shown that available money and word of mouth have significant effect on impulse buying while time pressure, variety of selection, store environment, and social norm have no significant effect on impulse buying.

Widayati et al., (2019) determined the effect of visual merchandising effect, sales promotion and positive emotion on impulse buying behavior. Data was collected from

155 respondents through a questionnaire by adopting purposive sampling technique and the data was analyzed with multiple linear regression analysis using the help of SPSS Version 23. The result of the study showed that visual merchandising variables and sales promotion variables had a significant effect on impulse buying variables while positive emotion variables did not influence the consumers impulse buying. On the other hand, Husnain et al., (2019) assessed the impact of situational variables categorized as personal factors (time availability, family influence, money availability) and in-store factors (store environment, sales promotions, and friendly store employees) on generation Y impulse buying behavior in the Pakistani context. A self-administered survey questionnaires was applied to gather information from 422 purposively selected respondents. SEM was used to analyze data with the aid of AMOS and SPSS 23. The results of the study revealed that personal factors with the exception money availability, time availability and family influence have significant and positive impact on the impulse buying behavior of generation Y consumers in Pakistan. And all in-store factors sales promotions, store environment and friendly employees have a significant positive impact on impulse buying behavior. The quantitative study conducted by Kaihatu (2019) to determine the effect of store (mall) environment and money availability on consumer impulse buying in the City of Tomorrow, Surabaya. Structured questionnaires were used as a source of primary data from 389 respondents using purposive sampling technique. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analysis data with the help of the SPSS. The results of the study indicated that the store (mall) environment has no effect on impulse buying while money availability has a positive and significant effect on consumer impulse buying.

Karim et al., (2020) conducted survey study to understand the effects of visual merchandising and price sensitivity on impulse purchase behavior with the mediating role of shopping enjoyment among young apparel shoppers at Dhaka city in Bangladesh. The study employed convenience sampling method to collected data using questionnaire from 305 young shopper respondents. The data was analyzed by deploying descriptive analysis and partial least squares- structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) methods using SPSS version 23.0 and Smart PLS software version 3.0. The study showed that visual merchandising (store layout, color, lighting, store design and cleanliness) and price sensitivity positively and significantly affects shoppers' shopping enjoyment and impulse purchase behavior, which shoppers' shopping enjoyment positively affects impulse purchase behavior. shoppers' shopping enjoyment has a mediating effect on impulse purchase behavior and the visual merchandising. shopping enjoyment has a mediating effect on price sensitivity and impulse purchase behavior. Lakshmi et al., (2020) investigated to identify the effect of situational factors on impulse buying in different retail formats of Food and Grocery retail in Bangalore, India. The study used structured questionnaires to gather data from randomly selected sample of 190 respondents. The data was analyzed using factor analysis and cluster analysis to segment the customers and notice the differences in impulsive buying behavior between the segments. And then ANOVA and Chi-square tests were used to determine the influence of each of the demographic variables on factors identified through factor analysis and across the identified segments. The finding indicated that situational variables like promotional activities, fliers, point-of sale events, and attractive aromas affect consumers impulse buying behaviors. On the case of demographic variables, working status is a demographic characteristic that influences impulse buying behavior generated by time and money

pressure and companies' sales promotional activities, while education significantly influences impulse buying behavior generated by sales-related activities.

Methods and Reviewing Process

Methods

This study has employed structured systematic literature review to achieve the stated objectives. The systematic literature review techniques used in this study was adopted from Transfield, Dyner and Smart (2003). This study used the articles published from year 2011 to 2020 for reviewing purpose. The relevant articles were searched and accompanied from the database by using keywords like consumer behavior, consumer buying/purchasing behavior, impulse buying and impulse buying behavior. To search for previous studies, key words was searched on google scholar, science direct, Emerald, ResearchGate, Taylor and Francis and Wiley database. Totally, 176 articles were extracted and found for reviewing purpose from the identified database. After collecting articles, the articles titles, abstracts, and full articles were reviewed for the sake of inclusion and exclusion of articles for further reviewing process. After excluding articles published before 2011, non-English, duplicated, and irrelevant articles 29 articles included in this systematic review study.

Figure 2: Article selection and refinement process.

Summary of reviewed articles and result presentation

This section presents the overall profile of the reviewed articles including database, year of publication, adopted research approach by researcher, journals articles published and country of origin.

Database

In the systematic literature review, after identifying the search term the next step is finding databases for searching an article. Accordingly, google scholar, Science Direct, Emerald, ResearchGate, wiley and Taylor and Francis group databases were used for searching and identifying articles for conducting this systematic literature review study.

As indicated figure 3 below, 28 percent of articles included under this review were extracted from google scholar, 28 percent of articles from ResearchGate, 14 percent of articles from Science direct, 14 percent from Emerald, 10 percent from Taylor and Francis group and the remaining 7 percent from Wiley online database.

Figure 3: Database for article extraction

Years of article publication

For this systematic literature review study, articles published between the year 2011 and 2020 were used. As it is indicated in the figure 4, 9 (31 percent) of extracted articles were published between the year 2011 and 2013, 7 (24 percent) articles reviewed in this study were published between 2014 and 2016 and the rest 13 (45 percent) articles were published between the year 2017 and 2020. As it is indicated around 70 percent of articles used in this systematic literature review study were published after the year 2014.

Figure 4: Years of article publication

Types of research approach

As indicated in figure 5 below majority of the articles included in this systematic article review study i.e., 93 % adopted quantitative research approach while the remaining 7% of articles involved in this study were employed qualitative research approach.

Figure 5 Types of research approach applied

Number of articles surveyed per journal

The articles used for this systematic review purpose were extracted from the following listed journal sources.

Table 1: Number of articles surveyed per journal

Journal	Frequency
The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research	2
European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences	1
European Journal of Scientific Research	1
International Journal of u- and e- Service, Science and Technology	1
Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business	1
European Journal of Business and Management Research	1
Journal of Business and Management	2
Global Business Review	1
Journal of Marketing Management	1
International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management	1
IC Social Science and Humanity	1
Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal	1
Applied Psychology: An International Review	1
International Journal of Sales & Marketing Management	1
Academic Research International	1
Marketing and Branding Research	1
Elixir Marketing Management	1
Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	2
Asian Journal of Business Management Studies	1
International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics	1
Advances in Hospitality and Tourism Research (AHTR)	1
Business and Economics Research Journal	1
Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences	1
International Journal of Economics and Management Studies	1
European Journal of Scientific Research	1
European Journal of Marketing	1
Total	29

Region where Study conducted

As it is viewed from the following figure 6, 17 percent of articles reviewed where conducted in Pakistan, 14 percent were conducted in India, 10 percent were conducted in Malaysia, 10 percent were conducted in USA, 7% percent were conducted Egypt, 7% percent were conducted in China, 7% percent were conducted in UK and the remaining were conducted in Ghana; Italy and other stated countries.

Figure 6: Country of Origin

Result discussion, Conclusion, and Implication

Result Discussion

Chang et al., (2011) claimed that ambient/ design characteristics of the retail environment affects impulse buying behavior. Other study also shown store ambient/design characteristics i.e., ambient, design, social and positive emotional have direct effects on impulse buying behavior (Chang et al., 2014). Likewise, Akram et al., (2016) conclude that store atmosphere has positive relationship and significant influence on impulse buying behavior. Parsad et al., (2017) in their study showed significant effect of store environment (crowd, sales employee, entertainment, lighting, aroma and display) on impulse buying. The store exterior atmospheric, visual merchandising, store interior atmospheric, store layout and store display has significant and positive effects on consumer impulse purchasing (Durai & Stella, 2020). Similarly, in-store atmosphere, in-store layout, sales-person, promotional activities, store environment and reference groups variables determine the consumer impulsive purchasing behavior (Arthur et al., 2020). Also the visual merchandising component (window display, in-store form/ mannequin display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage) is found to be statistically and significantly related to impulsive buying behavior (Chein et al., 2020). Accordingly, this study suggests the following hypothesis

H1. Store environment has positive and significant effect on impulse buying behavior

Chavosh et al., (2011) indicated that gender more popular among women rather than men, young consumers do more impulse buying rather than older consumers, people with a negative mood are more likely to do impulse buying. On the other hand, age has a significant negative relationship with the impulse buying behavior while gender and income are not significantly related with impulse buying (Ghani & Jan, 2011). Likewise, the study by Ekeng et al., (2012) shown that age of consumers and impulse buying were significantly and inversely related while impulse buying were differs significantly between male and female consumers with the impulse buying phenomenon is more

common among female consumers. The study also revealed that education has influence on impulse buying. On contrary, consumers characteristics like age, gender, income, geographical orientation and cultural orientation has no significant effect on consumers impulse buying(Ali & Hasnu, 2013). On the other hand, demographic characteristics i.e., income, gender, age, education, marital status had significant relationship with impulse buying behavior of consumers (Ugbohmhe et al., 2018). The demographically variable being youth, female, and higher household income were positively associated with impulsive buying. Therefore, there is disagreement among researchers with respect to the effect of a few demographic variables (education and income) on impulse buying behavior where future researchers must pay attention. Therefore, this study set the following assumptions

H2: Demographic factors has a significant effect on impulse buying behavior of consumers

Jyoti and Verma (2014) showed materialism, shopping enjoyment tendency, impulsive buying tendency, cultural construct of collectivism and two personality constructs of extraversion and neuroticism has significant positive relationship with impulsive buying behavior. The study shown that extrovert personalities are making more impulse purchases than other big personality trait(Mathai & Haridas, 2014; Veerayeekanna &Latha, 2016). The other study by Atulkar and Kesari (2017) indicated that impulse buying tendency, interpersonal influence, emotional attachment and materialism had significant positive relationship with impulsive buying. The study by Farid and Ali (2018) indicated the significant positive effects of openness, extraversion, conscientiousness and neuroticism while agreeableness had negative and insignificant effect on impulse buying behavior. Similarly high extraversion and neuroticism were positively associated with impulsive buying behavior (Creev &Furnham ,2019). Barakat (2019) indicated that there is significant and positive relationship between consumers' personal traits i.e., shyness, emotional instability, materialism, collectivism, and impulsive buying tendency. Bakar also showed that women consumers have greater tendency to impulsive buying than men consumers, young consumers have greater tendency to impulsive buying than old consumers and high-income consumers have greater tendency to impulsive buying than low-income consumers. Different studies have shown that personality traits had little contradicting finding where future researchers need to consider. Therefore, the study proposes the following assumption

H3: Personality trait has a significant effect on impulse buying decisions

Karbasivar and Yarahmadi (2011) exhibited the existence of positive relationship between the availability of credit card, promotional activities like cash discount and free product and consumer impulse buying behavior. According to Foroughi et al., (2012) the situational variables (money available and Time available) had influence on impulse buying. Similarly, Khorrami et al., (2015) shown that available money and word of mouth have significant effect on impulse buying while time pressure, variety of selection, store environment, and social norm have no significant effect on impulse buying. Accordingly, the study proposes the following assumptions

H4: Situational factors has a significant effect on the consumers impulse buying behaviors

Conclusion

Basically, in this systematic literature review study, the results show that among the demographic characteristics, gender, age, education and income have impact on the consumer's impulse buying behavior. Therefore, impulse buying seems like more common among women consumers than men consumers. Young age consumers are more involved in impulse buying than older and mature consumers while consumers with high-income have greater tendency to impulsive buying than low-income consumers.

Physical environment i.e., design, lighting, store location, product display which boost up impulsive buying behavior and a positive impact on impulse buying behavior. This indicates that store with good and attractive environment influences more customers to employ in impulsive buying. Therefore, ambient/design store characteristics, that is clean atmosphere and impressive interior store design may arouse positive emotions among consumers and encourage more impulse purchases.

Similarly, the study revealed the existences of significant relationship between personality traits and impulse buying behavior. Among Big five personality traits, two common personality constructs of extraversion and neuroticism has significant positive relationship with impulsive buying behavior. The extrovert personalities are making more impulse purchase among the Big five personality. Also, the other personality characteristics like impulse buying tendency, interpersonal influence, emotional attachment and materialism had significant impact on impulsive buying. Moreover, consumers' personal traits i.e., shyness, emotional stability, materialism, collectivism had significant effect on impulsive buying behavior.

The situational factors like the availability of time and money influences the impulse buying behavior. Moreover, the presence of promotional activities like cash discount and free trial.

Managerial and Theoretical implications

The study outcome could provide valuable insight for practical/managerial implications for managers or practitioners. The study had highlighted the importance of impact of demographic variables, store environment factors, personality traits and situational factors on impulse buying behavior of consumers. Therefore, the study will enable marketers to identify different consumer factors that influence them to buy impulsively. Consequently, the marketing organizations and companies must be able to stimulate/improve impulse buying decision making using a variety of marketing strategies that beneficial to boost sales and profits through impulsive buying behavior or actions of consumers.

This study provides two theoretical implications: a conceptual understanding of the consumers behavior and impulse buying process and factors that affect the consumers impulse buying behavior.

Limitation and Future study direction

This systematic reviewing study has certain limitations in spite the valuable results, indicating the need for further research. First, the covers the scope of study on the topic of impulse buying from traditional shopping scenarios perspective only without the inclusion of online shopping scenario. Second, the relatively small sample of articles were included for analysis. Third, motivational factors, perceptions and cultures may determine the impulse buying behavior which is not included in this study. Fourth, the study has shown many conflicting outcomes which are still unresolved and required future researchers' need to focus and have experimental study. Fifth, the study mainly focuses on literature review where future researchers are advised to test the proposed proposition during discussions of each variable.

References

- Ahmad, M. B., Ali, H. F., Malik, M. S., & Humayun, A. A. (2019). Factors Affecting Impulsive Buying Behavior with Mediating role of Positive Mood : An Empirical Study. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 8(1), 17–35.
- Ahmed, R. R., & Parmar, V. (2014). Factors influencing impulse buying behavior. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 100(3), 67–79.
- Ahn, J., & Kwon, J. (2020). The role of trait and emotion in cruise customers ' impulsive buying behavior : an empirical study. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 00(00), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2020.1810743>
- Ahuja, N. (2015). Effect of Branding On Consumer Buying Behaviour : A Study in Relation to Fashion Industry. *International Journal of Research in Humanities & Social Sciences*, 3(2), 32–37.
- Akram, U., Hui, P., Khan, M. K., & Hashim, M. (2016). Impact of Store Atmosphere on Impulse Buying Behaviour : Moderating Effect of Demographic Variables. *International Journal of U- and e- Service, Science and Technology*, 9(7), 43–60.
- Ali, A., & Hasnu, S. (2013). An analysis of consumers ' characteristics on impulse buying : evidence from pakistan Asim Ali – Corresponding Author MS in Management , Comsats Institute of Information Technology , *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(2), 560–570.
- Ali, M. A., & Zubairi, S. A. (2020). Impact of Demographic Factors on Impulse Buying Behavior : A Study of consumer behavior in Supermarkets of Karachi. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(3), 1–7.
- Amos, C., Holmes, G. R., & Keneson, W. C. (2013). Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services A meta-analysis of consumer impulse buying. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2013.11.004>
- Arthur, A., Owusu, I., & Boateng, E. D. (2020). Determinants of Consumer Impulsive Purchasing Behaviour in Medium-Large Shopping Malls in Ghana. *Open Journal*

of Business and Management, 8, 379–395.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2020.82024>

- Ashman, R., Solomon, M. R., & Wolny, J. (2015). An old model for a new age: Consumer decision making in participatory digital culture. *JOURNAL OF CUSTOMER BEHAVIOUR*, 14(2), 127–146.
<https://doi.org/10.1362/147539215X14373846805743>
- Atulkar, S., & Kesari, B. (2017). Impulse Buying : A Consumer Trait Prospective in Context of Central India. *Global Business Review*, 19(2), 1–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150917713546>
- Barakat, M. A. (2019). A Proposed Model for Factors Affecting Consumers ' Impulsive Buying Tendency in Shopping Malls. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 7(1), 120–134. <https://doi.org/10.15640/jmm.v7n1a10>
- Chang, H., Eckman, M., & Yan, R. (2011). The International Review of Retail , Distribution and Consumer Research Application of the Stimulus-Organism-Response model to the retail environment : the role of hedonic motivation in impulse buying behavior. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 21(3), 233–249.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09593969.2011.578798>
- Chang, H. J., Yan, R.-N., & Eckman, M. (2014a). Moderating effects of situational characteristics on impulse buying. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 42(4), 298–314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-04-2013-0074>
- Chang, H. J., Yan, R.-N., & Eckman, M. (2014b). Moderating effects of situational characteristics on impulse buying. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 42(4), 298–314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-04-2013-0074>
- Chavosh, A., Bagherzad, A., Namdar, J., Choshalyd, S. H., & Abbaspou, B. (2011). The Contribution of Product and Consumer Characteristics to Consumer ' s Impulse Purchasing Behaviour in Singapore. *2011 International Conference on Social Science and Humanity, April 2016*, 248–252.
- Chein, T. S., Hui, O. T., & Lee, C. J. (2020). Factors Affecting Impulsive Buying Behaviour – Evidence from Malaysia. *Global Business and Management Research: An International Journal Vol.*, 12(2).
- Cheng, Y., Chuang, S., Wang, S., & Kuo, S. (2013). The effect of companion ' s gender on impulsive purchasing : the moderating factor of cohesiveness and susceptibility to interpersonal influence. *Journal Of Applied Social Psychology*, 43, 227–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2012.00977.x>
- Creevy, M. F., & Furnham, A. (2019). Money Attitudes , Personality and Chronic Impulse Buying. *Applied Psychology*, 0(0), 1–16.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/apps.12215>

- Dixit, S. K., Lee, K., Loo, P. T., & Lee, K. (2019). Consumer behavior in hospitality and tourism. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 29(2), 151–161. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21639159.2019.1577159>
- Durai, T., & Stella, G. (2020). Store Atmospherics : an Effort to Influence Impulse Buying in. *International Journal of Sales & Marketing Management*, 10(1), 23–28.
- Ekeng, A. B., Lifu, F. L., & Asinya, F. A. (2012). Effect of Demographic Characteristics on Consumer Impulse Buying Among Consumers of Calabar Municipality , cross river state. *Academic Research International*, 3(2), 568–574.
- Farid, D. S., & Ali, M. (2018). Effects of Personality on Impulsive: Evidence from a Developing Country. *Marketing and Branding Research*, 5(1), 31–43.
- Foroughi, A., Buang, N. A., & Sherilou, M. (2012). Exploring the Influence of situational factors (money & time available) on impulse buying behaviour among different Ethnic. *Elixir Marketing Mgmt.*, 46, 8577–8580.
- Ghani, U., & Jan, F. A. (2011). An Exploratory Study of the Impulse Buying Behaviour of Urban Consumers in Peshawar. *International Conference on Business and Economics Research*, 1, 157–159.
- Goi, M. T., Kalidas, V., & Zeeshan, M. (2014). Comparison of Stimulus-Organism-Response Framework between International and Local Retailer. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 130, 461–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.054>
- Goodhope, O., Pcon, A., & Th, D. (2013). Major Classic Consumer Buying Behaviour Models : Implications for Marketing Decision-Making . *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(4), 164–173.
- H. Lakshmi, B.S. Harisha, & Narayana, L. (2020). Impact of Situational Factors on Impulse Buying in Food & Grocery. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 402–414.
- Harmancioglu, N., Finney, R. Z., & Joseph, M. (2009). Impulse purchases of new products : an empirical analysis. *Journal of Product & Brand Management* 18/1, 18(1), 27–37. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10610420910933344>
- Husnain, M., Rehman, B., Syed, F., & Akhtar, M. W. (2019). Personal and In-store Factors Influencing Impulse Buying Behavior among Generation Y Consumers of Small Cities Personal and In-store Factors Influencing Impulse Buying Behavior among Generation Y Consumers of Small Cities. *Business Perspectives and Research*, 7(1), 92–107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2278533718800625>
- Jisana, T. K. (2014). Consumer Behaviour Models : an overview. *Journal of Commerce & Management*, 1(5), 34–43.

- Jyoti, A., & Verma, A. (2014). Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services Intrinsic factors affecting impulsive buying behaviour — Evidence from India. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(4), 537–549.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.04.003>
- Jyoti, A., & Verma, A. (2015). Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services Does urge to buy impulsively differ from impulsive buying behaviour ? Assessing the impact of situational factors. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 22, 145–157.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.10.002>
- Kaihatu, T. S. (2019). How does the Store (mall) Environment and Money Availability Affect Consumer Impulse Buying Behavior at Surabaya City of tomorrow Shopping Center ? *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 4(2), 215–224.
- Kang, C. (2013). The Effects of Information Searching and Information Symmetry on Impulse Buying Decision. *The Journal of Global Business Management Volume*, 9(1), 196–203.
- Karbasivar, A., & Yarahmadi, H. (2011). Evaluating Effective Factors on Consumer Impulse Buying Behavior. *Asian Journal of Business Management Studies*, 2(4), 174–181.
- Karim, M. W., Haque, A., Juhdi, N. B., Muhibbullah, M., & Ulfy, M. A. (2020). The Effects of Visual Merchandising and Price Sensitivity on Impulse Purchase Behaviour among Young Apparel Shoppers in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Management*, 7(3), 192–202.
<https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.62.2020.73.192.202>
- Khan, M. T., Humayun, A. A., & Sajjad, M. (2015). Factors Affecting Impulse Buying and Percentage of Impulse Buying in Total Purchasing. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 7(1).
- Khorrami, M. S., Esfidani, M. R., & Delavari, S. (2015). The Effect of Situational Factors on Impulse Buying and Compulsive Buying : Clothing. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics Vol.*, 2(8), 823–837.
- Lee, J., & Johnson, K. K. P. (2015). Journal of Global Fashion Marketing : Bridging Fashion and Marketing Buying Fashion Impulsively : Environmental and Personal Influences Buying Fashion Impulsively : Environmental and Personal Influences. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 1(1), 30–39.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2010.10593055>
- Lu, P., & Su, C. (2018). A Study of the Factors Influencing Customers ' Impulse Buying Behavior in Restaurants. *Advances in Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 6(1), 47–67. <https://doi.org/10.30519/ahtr.421377>
- Made, N. I., & Ketut, R. I. (2018). Study of Influence of Store Environment on Impulse Buying Tendency. *RJOAS*, 10(82), 161–170.

- Mathai, S. T., & Haridas, R. (2014). Personality - its impact on impulse buying behaviour among the retail customers in Kochin city. *Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 16(4), 48–55.
- Maymand, M. M., & Ahmadinejad, M. (2011). Impulse buying : the role of store environmental stimulation and situational factors (An empirical investigation). *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(34), 13057–13065.
<https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM11.2112>
- Milner, T., & Rosenstreich, D. (2013). *A review of consumer decision-making models and development of a new model for financial services*.
- Osei, B. A., & Abenyin, A. N. (2018). Benjamin Appiah Osei & Ama Nyenkua. *Information Technology & Tourism*, 16(3), 265–284.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40558-016-0055-2>
- Ozdemir, E., & Akcay, G. (2019). The Effect of Gender Identity on Consumers ' Impulse Buying Behavior and The Moderating Role of Biological Sex. *Business and Economics Research Journal*, 10(5), 1109–1125.
<https://doi.org/10.20409/berj.2019.218>
- Parsad, C., Prashar, S., & Sahay, V. (2017). Impact of Impulsive Personality Traits and Store Environment on Impulse Buying Behavior. *Journal of Business and Management*, 23(1/2), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.6347/JBM.201709>
- Prasad, R. K., & Jha, M. K. (2014). Consumer buying decisions models : A descriptive study. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 6(3), 335–351.
- Ramya, N., & Ali, S. M. (2016). Factors affecting consumer buying behavior Factors affecting consumer buying behavior. *International Journal of Appl Ied Research*, 2(10), 76–80.
- Sadikoglu, G., & Sadikoglu, G. (2017). Modeling of Consumer Buying Behaviour Using Z- Number Concept Modeling of Consumer Buying Behaviour Using Z- Number Concept. *Intelligent Automation & Soft Computing*, 8587(July), 1–5.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10798587.2017.1327159>
- Tinne, W. S. (2010). Impulse Purchasing : A Literature Overview. *ASA University Review*, 4(2).
- Ugbomhe, U. O., Akhator, A. P., & Audu, E. D. (2018). Effects Of Demographic Factors On Impulse Buying Behaviour Of Consumers In Auchi, Edo State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 6(2).
- Veerayeeekanna, K., & Latha. (2016). The Influence of External Factors in Impulse Buying Behavior with Respect to Personality Traits. *International Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, 3(8), 10–12.

Widayati, C. C., Permana, H. A. D., & Riyad, M. (2019). The Effect of Visual Merchandising , Sales Promotion and Positive Emotion of Consumers on Impulse Buying Behavior. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 60, 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.7176/JMCR>

Wu, Y., & Li, E. Y. (2018). Marketing mix , customer value , and customer loyalty. *Internet Research*, 28(1), 74–104. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-08-2016-0250>

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